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Geography of COVID-19 Infections

Poverty and Vulnerability

Housing for Urban Poor

Land Use Planning and Consumption Pattern

Mobility, Class and Gender

Parking Demand Assessment

Inland Water Transportation

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Applying Integrated Approach of GIS and Landscape Metrics for Analysing Land Cover Dynamics of Varanasi District, India

Abstract

Traditionally, landscape metrics have been used to study the structure of the landscape, and ensuing changes in its structure over time at different levels. Landscape metrics-based such type of studies have been mainly confined to scientists and researchers of the environment or ecology. It has not been so popular under the subject area of geography as much as among ecologists. Therefore, the use of the landscape metrics should be encouraged along with traditional GIS-based land use and land cover studies in geography; so that, as a geographer, we can explore the spatial pattern of land transformations along with its structural nature because only spatial study of changes in the area is not enough, their structure is also important. Keeping the above thought in mind, the present study has attempted to use GIS-based supervised classification and landscape metrics in integrated modus to conduct a spatio-temporal study of the land covers of the Varanasi district from the period of 2000 to 2020. It uses USGS's Landsat ETM+ (Year-2000) and OLI (Year-2020) data along with six class-level (CA, NP, MPS, CLUMPY, PLAND, and nLSI) and two landscape-level (SHIDI, and SIDI) metrics. Therefore, ERDAS v.2015, ArcGIS v.10.7 and fragstats v.4.2 have been used to classify satellite images and calculate landscape metrics. The result shows that Varanasi district had the maximum decreases in the areas of vegetation cover, water body, and agricultural land while the maximum increase was observed in built-up land and vacant land. Along with this, there has been a rapid change in the patch structure, shape and distribution of different types of land covers so the diversity has increased at the landscape level in the study area.

Introduction:

The land is the basis of the socio-economic development of all societies or communities [Wu et al., 2013; Long et al., 2007; Nha, D.V., 2017; Gomes et al., 2020]. Socio-economic development is the act of transforming the natural landscape of the respective place into a cultural landscape [Song et al., 2020]. The rate of this socio-economic development determines the intensity of the dynamics of the changing landscape of the related land [Schmitz et al., 2012;]. Therefore, the landscape is a system of rapid changes in the present time, which is visible to us as a changing land cover. This changing land cover itself is affected by local socio-economic activities and also

affects it [Kiswanto et al., 2018; Kumi et al., 2021]. Its most obvious form revealed as the peri-urban areas between the city and its hinterland [Czekajlo et al., 2021; Spyra et al., 2021; Gomes et al., 2020; Tian Li, 2015; Kombe et al., 2005]. Therefore, it is necessary to study the land cover and its dynamics based on a logical and scientific approach in the changing physical and socio-economic changes of the place [Uisso et al., 2021 & Omaid et al., 2017]. The dynamics of land cover and land use give rise to many adverse effects along with human progress and development [Freitas et al., 2010; Grigoras G. & Uritescu B., 2019; Schlindwein et al., 2021]. Thus, numerous literary texts and research papers exist, which present the study of changes in land use and land cover as a necessary condition to understand both these negative and positive effects. Thus, land use and land cover transformation are one of the significant forces shaping terrestrial systems at the global and local levels [Meyer & Turner, 1992; Turner & Meyer, 1994; Verburg et al., 2011]. Therefore, to promote the development and sustainable use of land resources, it becomes essential to know and understand the historical and current status of the land transformation taking place in these land landscapes, in which remote sensing and GIS-based geographical study of land use and land cover provide extraordinary support [Abdulrahman et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2018; Theissen et al., 2019; Mbow et al., 2021; Andriamihaja et al., 2021; Goh et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2021]. Available literature shows that many methods and techniques of land use and land cover have developed along with technological development. Most of which based on remote sensing and GIS [Civco et al., 2002; Szuster et al., 2011; Giri, 2012; Alqurashi & Kumar, 2013; Yang et al., 2014]. Studies have shown that integrated methodology of remote sensing, GIS and landscape metrics can play an essential role in studying land use and land cover changes. The available research work evidenced this fact, in which an attempt has been made to analyse and study the land use and land cover by using GIS and landscape metrics in an integrated way [Herzog & Lausch, 2001; Herold et al., 2002; Liu et al., 2013; Liu & Weng, 2013; Sertel et al., 2018]. Land use and land cover change refer to the expansion or shrinking of different land use land cover categories under the influence of human activities during various socio-economic development processes [Meyer & Turner, 1992]. Several landscape metrics have been developed to quantitatively analyse the expansion or shrinking that occurs in different land cover classes of landscape in a particular region [McGarigal, 1995]. Therefore, analysis of the variations in the pattern of land cover by the use of GIS and landscape metrics seems to be appropriate from the scientific point of view [Lamine et al., 2018], on the basis of which the configuration and nature of the land cover pattern of the

respective area can be understood with more precision [McGarigal, 1995; Lausch & Herzog, 2002; Herold et al., 2002; Uemaa et al., 2009; Leitão et al., 2012; McGarigal, 2014].

Keeping in view the above facts, the landscape metrics have been used along with GIS methodology to analyse the land cover pattern of Varanasi district (India) at the macro and micro level (at the development block). In this work, to avoid metrics redundancy, six metrics at class level and five metrics at landscape level have been selected. This research uses ArcGIS v.10.7, ERDAS v.2015 for classification and mapping of land cover and FRAGSTATS v.4.2 for landscape metrics-based analysis of that classified image.

Figure:1

Study Area:

The geographical extent of the Varanasi district lies between 25°15' N to 25°22' N latitudes and 82°57' E to 83°01' E longitudes. The total geographical area of the Varanasi district is 153317.35 hectares (Figure: 1). Topographically, most of the study area consists of featureless old alluvial

plains, with average elevation ranging from 70 m in the east to 90 m in the west. The Ganga River is the principal river of the study area. It flows along the eastern boundary of the study area. In addition to the Ganga River, the Varuna River flows in the central part of the study area and the Gomti River in the northern part. According to Census 2011, Varanasi district has 18 places at the state level, with 43.4% urban population and 22.3% rural population. The population density here is 2395 persons per square kilometer. There are 1295 villages in the study area, of which only 37 are uninhabited villages. The study area belongs to most of the rural part.

Figure-2: Methodology for Land Cover Study

Result & Discussion

In the present paper, the land cover analysis done at macro and micro level (block level) of Varanasi district is as follows:

Table: 1

Growth Rate in Different Land Covers (2000-2020)						
Adm. Area	Growth Rate in Agr. Land	Growth Rate in Built-up Land	Growth Rate in Sandy Area (Riverine)	Growth Rate in Vacant Land	Growth Rate in Veg. Cover	Growth Rate in Water Body
<i>1</i>	0.60%	567.14%	-100.00%	-15.69%	-45.16%	-52.74%
<i>2</i>	-4.32%	325.78%	-100.00%	18.77%	-44.40%	-13.71%
<i>3</i>	-12.34%	413.67%	-2.34%	78.51%	-59.18%	-13.21%
<i>4</i>	-2.03%	425.63%	-45.71%	41.54%	-70.07%	-39.66%
<i>5</i>	-15.19%	615.21%	-100.00%	43.61%	-45.10%	-21.00%
<i>6</i>	-21.67%	265.23%	55.62%	-1.15%	-42.16%	-8.40%
<i>7</i>	-1.53%	366.31%	-100.00%	0.75%	-41.25%	-18.94%
<i>8</i>	0.09%	528.11%	-100.00%	3.26%	-53.11%	24.82%
<i>9</i>	-78.66%	68.17%	-26.00%	-26.40%	-61.25%	0.03%
<i>10</i>	-6.47%	196.29%	-7.70%	11.69%	-50.95%	-16.54%

Note: 1-Arajilne Block, 2- Baragaon Block, 3-Chirai Gaon, 4-Cholapur Block, 5-Harhua Block, 6-kashi Vidyapith Block, 7- Pindra Block, 8-Sewapuri Block, 9-Varanasi City, 10- Total District.

Table: 2

Land Cover Transformation (in %)								
Land Cover Class	Agricultural Land	Built-up Land	Sandy Area (Riverine)	Year- 2020		Vegetation Cover	Water Body	Grand Total
				Vacant Land				
Agricultural Land	80.36	3.84	0.21	13.73	1.75	0.11	100.00	
Built-up Land	0.60	98.18	0.26	0.50	0.33	0.14	100.00	
Sandy Area (Riverine)	19.06	2.51	64.09	1.29	1.25	11.80	100.00	
Vacant Land	32.96	20.23	0.18	42.89	3.42	0.32	100.00	
Vegetation Cover	40.64	9.15	0.75	28.45	20.47	0.55	100.00	
Water Body	5.68	2.94	18.31	3.08	0.99	69.01	100.00	
Grand Total	179.30	136.85	83.78	89.94	28.20	81.92	600.00	

Agricultural Land

The analysis shows that during the year 2000 to 2020, there was a negative growth rate of -6.00 percent under agricultural land (Table 1). During this, the agricultural land was reduced from

105546.61 hectares to 98654.51 hectares. Simultaneously, the landscaped metric-based analysis shows that the patch count under agricultural land decreased from 5753 to 3827, and the average patch size increased from 18.35 to 25.78 hectares (Table 3).

Table: 3

<i>Agricultural Land</i>												
Adm. Area	CA		PLAND		NP		MPS		CLUMPY		nLSI	
	Year-2000	Year-2020										
1	15293.18	15385.50	80.13	76.30	563	352	27.16	43.54	0.71	0.81	0.22	0.14
2	12212.67	11685.50	74.72	71.47	529	320	23.09	36.52	0.79	0.81	0.15	0.14
3	11672.99	10233.10	66.04	57.92	539	662	21.66	15.46	0.87	0.87	0.09	0.07
4	15775.87	15455.57	75.20	73.61	562	370	28.07	41.77	0.81	0.83	0.14	0.13
5	9967.14	8453.36	73.56	62.36	470	531	21.21	15.92	0.79	0.82	0.15	0.11
6	9005.61	7053.86	58.37	42.43	1065	825	8.46	8.55	0.84	0.87	0.09	0.07
7	18185.79	17906.71	75.96	74.78	584	335	31.14	53.45	0.79	0.81	0.16	0.14
8	12283.87	12294.47	81.20	73.21	423	325	29.04	37.83	0.76	0.81	0.20	0.14
9	1149.48	245.28	15.74	3.37	708	432	1.62	0.57	0.85	0.77	0.12	0.22
10	105546.61	98713.35	68.80	64.36	5753	3827	18.35	25.78	0.83	0.85	0.12	0.09

Note: 1-Arajiline Block, 2- Baragaon Block, 3-Chirai Gaon, 4-Cholapur Block, 5-Harhua Block, 6-kashi Vidyapith Block, 7- Pindra Block, 8-Sewapuri Block, 9-Varanasi City, 10- Total District.

At the same time, the patterns of reducing patch number and increasing patch size indicate that large agricultural land has expanded over other land cover types present in its interior. In contrast, smaller agricultural land has changed to other land covers. The values of the CLUMPY index and nLSI confirm the above statement along with the trend of aggregation in agricultural land. The decreasing value of the PLAND index shows that the dominance of agricultural land has decreased in the study area, mainly due to the conversion of small agricultural land into other land cover classes. During the study period, 80.36% of the total agricultural land remained in its original form while 19.64% changed to other land cover types. The maximum change was in the vacant land category (13.73%), and the least change was in the water body category (0.11%) (Table 2). The sub-district level analysis shows that the highest negative growth rate under agricultural land was seen in Varanasi city, and the lowest negative growth rate was in Pindra block (-1.53%). Apart from the above, a marginal increase has been registered under agricultural land in Arajiline (0.60%) and Sewapuri (0.09%) development blocks (Table 1).

The pattern of patch number and average patch size shows that the pattern of agricultural land in Chiraigaon and Harhua development blocks is scattered. The reason for this seems to be the change of agricultural land into other land covers. Apart from these, the average size of agricultural land has increased in all other development blocks as well as their aggregation has increased. The CLUMPY index and nLSI value also reflect the above characteristics. The PLAND index shows that the most rapid reduction in agricultural land occurred in Kashi Vidyapith Block and Varanasi City (Table 3).

Built-up Land

In contrast to agricultural land, built-up land registered a growth rate of 196.29% (Table 1); the built-up land increased from 4909.78 hectares to 14547.04 hectares during this period. The study found that the number of built-up land patches risen from 6433 to 21059, and the average patch size decreased from 0.76 hectares to 0.69 hectares. From which it is clear that between the year 2000 and 2020, there has been a tendency to expand rapidly in built-up land. An increase in the CLUMPY index and a decrease in the nLSI indicate that older patches of built-up land have been compacted over time. This compactness occurred due to expanding built-up land over the other land cover classes located between older built-lands. Similarly, the value of PLAND has increased in the year 2020 compared to the year 2000, which shows that the dominancy of built-up land has risen rapidly in the study area (Table 4).

At this time, built-land spread rapidly on other land covers. Between 2000 and 2020, 98.18% of built-up land remained in its original form; only 1.82% of built-up land was transformed into other land-cover classes (Table 2). Analysis at the sub-district level shows that the highest growth rate under built-up land was in Harhua block (615.21%) and the lowest in Varanasi city (68.17%). The pattern of the NP shows that during the study period, the maximum growth of built-up land in the dispersed form occurred in the Arajiline development block and with maximum concentration under Varanasi city. The maximum increase under the average patch size was recorded under Varanasi city, indicating that the built-up land in Varanasi city has expanded with maximum compactness compared to other parts and in Cholapur development block with the lowest compactness (Table 4).

Table: 4

Adm. Area	<i>Built-up Land</i>											
	<i>CA</i>		<i>NP</i>		<i>MPS</i>		<i>PLAND</i>		<i>CLUMPY</i>		<i>nLSI</i>	
	<i>Year-2000</i>	<i>Year-2020</i>	<i>Year-2000</i>	<i>Year-2020</i>	<i>Year-2000</i>	<i>Year-2020</i>	<i>Year-2000</i>	<i>Year-2020</i>	<i>Year-2000</i>	<i>Year-2020</i>	<i>Year-2000</i>	<i>Year-2020</i>
<i>1</i>	190.80	1272.91	675	3291	0.28	0.39	1.26	6.31	0.68	0.71	0.32	0.27
<i>2</i>	142.57	607.04	636	2333	0.22	0.26	0.87	3.71	0.66	0.66	0.34	0.33
<i>3</i>	198.85	1021.43	626	2283	0.32	0.45	1.12	5.78	0.65	0.71	0.34	0.27
<i>4</i>	144.10	757.43	459	2373	0.31	0.32	0.69	3.61	0.57	0.67	0.42	0.32
<i>5</i>	159.61	1141.55	558	2390	0.29	0.48	1.18	8.43	0.62	0.72	0.38	0.25
<i>6</i>	916.29	3346.58	1168	2920	0.78	1.15	6.71	20.15	0.79	0.80	0.19	0.16
<i>7</i>	197.34	920.21	727	2745	0.27	0.34	0.82	3.84	0.56	0.70	0.43	0.29
<i>8</i>	109.07	685.11	581	2457	0.19	0.28	1.07	4.08	0.69	0.66	0.30	0.32
<i>9</i>	2851.15	4794.79	847	546	3.37	8.78	39.17	65.80	0.86	0.83	0.08	0.11
<i>10</i>	4909.78	14547.04	6433	21059	0.76	0.69	3.20	9.48	0.82	0.80	0.18	0.18

Note: 1-Arajiline Block, 2- Baragaon Block, 3-Chirai Gaon, 4-Cholapur Block, 5-Harhua Block, 6-kashi Vidyapith Block, 7- Pindra Block, 8-Sewapuri Block, 9-Varanasi City, 10- Total District.

Similarly, the CLUMPY index and nLSI values pattern shows that the compactness has increased due to aggregation of built-up land in Arajiline, Baragaon, Chiraigaon, Cholapur Harhua, Kashi Vidyapith, and Pindra block. In contrast, the built-up land expanded as in the dispersed pattern in Sewapuri block and Varanasi city. The maximum increase in the value of PLAND took place in Varanasi city and Kashi Vidyapith block. In both of these, the dominance of built-up land increased rapidly, and its size increased (Table 4).

Sandy Area (Riverine)

Like the agricultural land, the sandy area also saw a negative growth rate (-7.70%) from 2000 to 2020 (Table 1). The sandy area decreased from 2783.33 hectares to 2569.05 hectares during this period. The spatial pattern shows that the sandy area is found only in the eastern parts of Varanasi city, Chiraigaon, Cholapur, and Kashi Vidyapith development blocks. In this period, the pattern of NP and MPS shows that the formation of new patches did not cause spatial growth in sandy areas. Instead, it grew by the infilling process in the old patches and also grew along their edges. The CLUMPY index and nLSI patterns also show that the sandy area has grown along its patch edges and not by newly dispersed patches. The PLAND value indicates that the spatial dominance of the sandy area has decreased in the study area. The table 2 shows that 64.09% of the sandy area

remained unchanged at this time while 35.91% changed to other land covers. Most of the sandy area transformed into agricultural land (19.06%) and water body (11.80%).

At the sub-district level, the sandy area's optimistic growth rate was only in the Kashi Vidyapith block (55.62%), and all other parts had a negative growth rate. The pattern of NP shows that the maximum decline in patch numbers was recorded in the Cholapur block and the lowest in the Kashi Vidyapith block. The pattern of MPS shows that the average patch size of the sandy area has the highest increase in Varanasi city and the lowest in Cholapur block. Apart from these, the average patch size also increased in Chiraigaon and Kashi Vidyapith blocks (Table 5).

Table: 5

<i>Sandy Area (Riverine)</i>												
Adm. Area	<i>CA</i>		<i>NP</i>		<i>MPS</i>		<i>PLAND</i>		<i>CLUMPY</i>		<i>nLSI</i>	
	<i>Year-2000</i>	<i>Year-2020</i>										
1	3.02	0.00	22	0	0.14	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.70	0.00	0.30	0.00
2	1.88	0.00	15	0	0.13	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.37	0.00
3	1663.18	1624.26	202	175	8.23	9.28	9.42	9.19	0.94	0.95	0.05	0.05
4	645.53	350.43	323	120	2.00	2.92	3.08	1.67	0.85	0.86	0.14	0.14
5	2.86	0.00	23	0	0.12	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.37	0.00
6	311.49	484.75	109	108	2.86	4.49	1.98	2.92	0.95	0.93	0.05	0.07
7	6.31	0.00	36	0	0.18	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.69	0.00	0.31	0.00
8	0.95	0.00	7	0	0.14	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.79	0.00	0.21	0.00
9	148.13	109.61	100	24	1.48	4.57	2.03	1.50	0.96	0.97	0.04	0.03
10	2783.33	2569.05	854	424	3.26	6.06	1.82	1.68	0.92	0.93	0.07	0.07

Note: 1-Arajiline Block, 2- Baragaon Block, 3-Chirai Gaon, 4-Cholapur Block, 5-Harhua Block, 6-kashi Vidyapith Block, 7- Pindra Block, 8-Sewapuri Block, 9-Varanasi City, 10- Total District.

The sandy area grew on other land covers located in its intermediate parts and along the edges of the old existing patches in these four areas. CLUMPY index and nLSI also show the above result. The obtained values of the PLAND index show that the spatial dominancy of the sandy area has increased in the Kashi Vidyapith block of the study area and has decreased in other parts of the study area. Most of it has been converted into other land covers. In four parts of the study area - Arajiline, Baragaon, Harhua, Pindra, and Sewapuri development blocks, the entire area of the sandy area was transformed into other land covers, which means the sandy area lost its spatial dominancy in these areas (Table 5).

Vacant Land

The growth rate under vacant land was 11.69% during the study period (Table 1). In the year 2000 to 2020, it had increased from 26977.85 hectares to 30130.85 hectares, showing that due to urban expansion, the land was to be left as the empty plot for the fulfillment of residential and commercial purposes. The pattern of NP and MPS shows that there was a rapid increase in the form of scattered and transformation of other land covers into vacant land during the study period. CLUMPY index and nLSI also show the above patterns. The PLAND pattern indicates that the spatial dominance of the vacant land has increased with the rapid increase in the dispersed patches of vacant land in the study area. At this time, 42.89% of vacant land remained in its original form without any transformation, while 57.11% of vacant land was transformed into other land covers. Of the total conversions that took place, the most significant transformation of vacant land occurred into agricultural (32.96%) and built-up land (20.23%) (Table 2).

The data obtained at the sub-district level shows that the growth rate of vacant land was negative in Varanasi city, Arajiline, and Kashi Vidyapith development blocks of the study area. Apart from these, the growth rate of vacant land in Baragaon, Chiraigaon, Cholapur, Harhua, Pindra, and Sewapuri blocks was positive. The main reason behind this in these areas has been converting vacant land into other land uses such as built-up land.

Table: 6

<i>Vacant Land</i>												
Adm. Area	CA		NP		MPS		PLAND		CLUMPY		nLSI	
	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020
1	3226.72	2720.59	4588	3457	0.70	0.79	13.30	13.49	0.72	0.73	0.24	0.23
2	2887.13	3428.99	2840	2967	1.02	1.16	17.67	20.97	0.78	0.76	0.18	0.19
3	1917.19	3422.36	2090	2017	0.92	1.70	10.84	19.38	0.78	0.77	0.19	0.18
4	2622.29	3711.55	2767	3228	0.95	1.15	12.50	17.68	0.78	0.76	0.19	0.20
5	2317.56	3328.21	2400	2584	0.97	1.29	17.09	24.57	0.78	0.73	0.19	0.20
6	4470.57	4419.05	3353	2918	1.33	1.51	23.67	26.59	0.77	0.74	0.18	0.19
7	4382.95	4415.70	4106	4370	1.07	1.01	18.30	18.44	0.79	0.76	0.17	0.19
8	3005.34	3103.33	3562	2762	0.84	1.12	13.21	18.48	0.74	0.76	0.23	0.20
9	2148.10	1581.06	1206	1529	1.78	1.03	29.50	21.71	0.77	0.74	0.16	0.20
10	26977.85	30130.85	23969	25141	1.13	1.20	17.60	19.65	0.78	0.75	0.18	0.20

Note: 1-Arajiline Block, 2- Baragaon Block, 3-Chirai Gaon, 4-Cholapur Block, 5-Harhua Block, 6-kashi Vidyapith Block, 7- Pindra Block, 8-Sewapuri Block, 9-Varanasi City, 10- Total District.

The Landscape Index-based analysis shows that the MPS has increased along with the decrease in the NP of vacant land in Arajiline, Chiraigaon, Kashi Vidyapith, and Sewapuri development blocks of the study area. Therefore, the increase in the area of vacant land in these development blocks has been of compact nature. On the contrary, an increase in the NP of vacant land was recorded in Varanasi city and Pindra block. Along with this, it was also found that there has been an increase in MPS in both these blocks (Table 6).

Therefore, the increases in vacant land in both these development blocks were dispersed or scattered in nature. Apart from this, the remaining areas (Baragaon, Cholapur, and Harhua development blocks) registered an increase in both the NP and MPS. In these parts, the vacant land expanded along the edges of the old existing patch and encroachment over other land covers located in the inner part of these old patches and the formation of new small patches. The obtained values of the CLUMPY index, nLSI, and PLAND also support this (Table 6).

Vegetation Cover

In the years 2000 to 2020, the growth rate of vegetation cover was -50.95% (Table 1). The vegetation cover decreased from 10219.80 hectares to 5012.37 hectares during this period. The analysis shows that the reduction under vegetation cover in the study area was the highest among all other land covers. The total NP of vegetation cover decreased from 22684 to 17170 during this period, and the MPS also decreased from 0.45 hectares to 0.29 hectares. These results clarify that there has been rapid fragmentation of the vegetation cover in the study area and has become more and more dispersed distribution. The values of the CLUMPY index and nLSI also showed a decrease during this period. They show that large areas of pre-existing vegetation cover have contracted rapidly, and vegetation cover distribution has become increasingly dispersed. Similarly, the value of PLAND also decreased from 6.66 to 3.27 (Table 7).

Therefore, due to the rapid destruction of vegetation cover in the study area, its spatial dominance decreased significantly. The main reason for this is the rapid change of vegetation cover to other land covers. Only 20.47% of the vegetation cover remained free from all types of land transformation during the study period, whereas 79.63% changed to other land covers. The maximum transformation of vegetation cover occurred into agricultural (40.64%) and vacant lands (28.45%) (Table 2). The figure shows that there has been a decrease in the NP and MPS of the

vegetation cover in all parts of the Varanasi district, which proves the decrease in the vegetation cover (Table 7).

Table: 7

<i>Vegetation Cover</i>												
Adm. Area	CA		NP		MPS		PLAND		CLUMPY		nLSI	
	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020
1	1387.60	760.92	3342	2678	0.42	0.28	5.11	3.78	0.69	0.67	0.30	0.31
2	1039.32	577.91	2380	2056	0.44	0.28	6.36	3.53	0.72	0.67	0.26	0.32
3	1201.04	490.32	2271	1736	0.53	0.28	6.79	2.78	0.75	0.69	0.23	0.31
4	1186.95	355.31	3083	1496	0.38	0.24	5.66	1.69	0.70	0.66	0.28	0.34
5	1011.58	555.40	2146	1810	0.47	0.31	7.46	4.10	0.73	0.70	0.25	0.29
6	1284.12	742.69	2919	2364	0.44	0.31	5.71	4.47	0.68	0.69	0.30	0.29
7	1090.64	640.80	3033	2433	0.36	0.26	4.56	2.68	0.71	0.67	0.28	0.32
8	1311.99	615.20	3031	2194	0.43	0.28	4.30	3.66	0.65	0.67	0.33	0.31
9	706.56	273.82	1208	578	0.58	0.47	9.70	3.76	0.74	0.74	0.23	0.25
10	10219.80	5012.37	22684	17170	0.45	0.29	6.66	3.27	0.73	0.68	0.26	0.31

Note: 1-Arajiline Block, 2- Baragaon Block, 3-Chirai Gaon, 4-Cholapur Block, 5-Harhua Block, 6-kashi Vidyapith Block, 7- Pindra Block, 8-Sewapuri Block, 9-Varanasi City, 10- Total District.

The pattern of the CLUMPY index and nLSI in Varanasi city and Arajiline, Baragaon, Chiraigaon, Cholapur, Harhua, and Pindra development blocks of the study area shows that the vegetation cover in these parts has become more and more dispersed in nature. Apart from these, the vegetation cover in Kashi Vidyapith and Sewapuri blocks has sunk rapidly to its old places. The decreased value of PLAND in all parts of the study area indicates that vegetation cover's spatial dominance has reduced and is quickly changing to other land covers (Table 7).

Water Body

During this period, the growth rate of the water body was -16.54%, in which the area of the water body decreased from 2879.99 hectares to 2403.54 hectares (Table 1). The main reason for this reduction has been the destruction of old water sources like ponds and small drains. The pattern of NP and MPS of the water body also shows that the surface sources of the water body have shriveled and been destroyed. The main reason for the increase in MPS is the spatial change over time in the river course and water flow. The values of the CLUMPY index and nLSI also show that small water bodies in the study area are rapidly drying up and are mainly confined to their larger areas

like rivers and large ponds etc. PLAND also shows that the spatial dominance of water bodies has decreased in the study area (Table 8). During this period, 69.01% of the water body area remained in its original form, and 30.99% changed to other land covers. The maximum transformation of the water body occurred into the sandy area (18.31%), and the minimum was in vegetation cover (0.99%) (Table 2).

At the sub-district level, the increase in the water body area was recorded only in Varanasi city (0.03%) and Sewapuri block (24.82%). Apart from these two, there was a decrease in the water body area in all other parts. The maximum reduction in water body area occurred in the Arajiline block while the least in Kashi Vidyapith, which were -54.72% and -8.40%, respectively. The decrease in NP and MPS of the water body was observed in three development blocks- Arajiline, Baragaon, and Pindra of the study area, which reflect the gradual depletion of the water body over time in these areas (Table 8).

Table: 8

Adm. Area	Water Body											
	CA		NP		MPS		PLAND		CLUMPY		nLSI	
	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020	Year-2000	Year-2020
1	50.92	24.07	156	67	2.12	0.36	0.18	0.12	0.68	0.74	0.32	0.26
2	59.19	51.08	129	71	1.16	0.72	0.36	0.31	0.73	0.82	0.27	0.18
3	1007.27	874.24	188	51	1.15	17.14	5.78	4.95	0.94	0.95	0.06	0.04
4	606.57	366.03	107	75	1.66	4.88	2.87	1.74	0.92	0.89	0.08	0.11
5	94.16	74.39	94	38	1.27	1.96	0.69	0.55	0.76	0.77	0.24	0.23
6	624.87	572.38	187	85	1.09	6.73	3.56	3.45	0.94	0.96	0.05	0.04
7	78.83	63.90	153	116	1.23	0.55	0.33	0.27	0.76	0.79	0.23	0.21
8	77.34	96.53	142	56	0.80	1.72	0.22	0.57	0.61	0.81	0.39	0.19
9	280.84	280.93	81	28	1.00	10.03	3.86	3.85	0.91	0.92	0.09	0.08
10	2879.99	2403.54	1164	551	1.20	4.36	1.92	1.57	0.91	0.92	0.09	0.08

Note: 1-Arajiline Block, 2- Baragaon Block, 3-Chirai Gaon, 4-Cholapur Block, 5-Harhua Block, 6-kashi Vidyapith Block, 7- Pindra Block, 8-Sewapuri Block, 9-Varanasi City, 10- Total District.

The remaining parts showed a decrease in the value of NP and an increase in the value of MPS, indicating that the areas along the edge of its old patches in the water body had increased. The values of the CLUMPY index and nLSI also show that the water body area has decreased, and they are gradually disappearing from the study area. The PLAND value indicates that the spatial

dominance of surface water has increased in the Sewapuri block and Varanasi city of the study area. In contrast, it has decreased in the rest of the areas (Table 8).

SHDI & SIDI

The increasing values of SHDI and SIDI show that the patches under all the land covers in the study area have changed rapidly and have become dispersed in nature, due to which the diversity has increased at the landscape level in the study area. At the sub-district level, the decrease in the values of SHDI and SIDI in Varanasi city and Cholaipur block shows that there has been a decrease in the diversity at the landscape level in both these areas. In contrast, in the rest of the regions, the values of SHDI and SIDI increased, showing increasing diversity at the landscape level (Figure 4).

Figure: 4

Conclusion:

There are many important literatures argue that the analysis and study of land use and land cover has a distinctive role in developing an appropriate and rational understanding about the environmental changes and development actions taking place at the global or local level. Due to human intervention, the pattern of the land cover of a particular place has changed drastically, especially in the peri-regions. Due to these changes, the size, composition, structure and area of different patches of land cover changes significantly. Therefore, as a geographer, we must lay emphasis on conducting studies integrating landscape metrics-based analysis with the traditional study methodology of land use and land cover, so that we can get a more clear and rational

knowledge of the land cover present in the study area. So, in the present study, an attempt has been made to analyze the land cover of Varanasi district emphasizing this idea. This study suggests that integrating landscape metrics with GIS-based visual interpretation appears more rational to interpret the spatial pattern of land cover along with the pattern of the patch-level structure of that land covers. Socio-economic and political factors should also be integrated with the above methodology so that a more accurate and logical interpretation of land use and land cover can be made. The results obtained from this type of study can be used in land assessment, environmental studies and planning for rational use of natural resources and their management.

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